

Proposed Solutions Regarding Work Overload for the Marketing Division of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat

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ABSTRACT: Football is a sport that is very popular in every level of Indonesian society. Indonesia is known as a country with a very large number of soccer fans. Indonesia has the fourth largest population in the world with 265 million people, and according to Nielsen Sport, 77% of Indonesia's population has an interest in football. This fact makes Indonesia the country with the third largest number of football fans. The Indonesian soccer market is huge, and soccer is a big business opportunity in Indonesia. PT Persib Bandung Bermartabat oversees the Persib Bandung football club which is one of the Indonesian teams. PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat located at Graha Persib Floor 3 Jalan Sulanjana No 17 Bandung. In managing a company, of course, requires human resources who have high ability to help achieve company goals. In addition, to be able to form a good performing club, of course, you must have a healthy management ecosystem as well. This study uses a mixed method qualitative and quantitative research model. In quantitative research, the authors distribute questionnaires in the form of g-forms to marketing department employees using the National Aeronautics and Space Administration Task Load Index (NASA – TLX) method to measure the workload experienced by employees. In the qualitative method the author conducted interviews with observations of the organizational structure and job descriptions of employees in the marketing department of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat using Semi- Structural Interviews. In finding the root of the problem the author uses CRT (Current Reality Tree). The results of this study are the organizational structure and job descriptions that are made based on benchmark results with 3 football club management. The author proposes a new organizational structure and job descriptions which in the end can be adapted to the needs of the marketing division of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat to be able to help realize strategic initiatives and solve problems experienced.

KEYWORDS: Human Resources, Job description, Workload, Nasa-TLX, Current Reality Tree (CRT), Organizational Structure.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is known for having a large number of football fans. Indonesia has the world's fourth-largest population, Indonesia has a population of 265 million people, and according to Nielsen Sport, 77% of the population is interested in football. As a result of these facts, Indonesia has the third most football fans in the world. Every football team in Indonesia has a sizable fan base, and fans and the merchandise of their favorite team are inextricably linked (Berawi et al 2018; Zhou et al 2020). The company that manages the Indonesian football team Persib Bandung Football Club and the basketball team Prawira Bandung is PT Persib Bandung Bermartabat. Aside from that, they own and operate a company that produces and sells official Persib merchandise. Persib is one of Indonesia's most popular football clubs (Johnson et al 2005). Of course, managing a company necessitates the use of highly capable human resources to assist in the achievement of company objectives. Based on preliminary findings at PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat is known that the workload on each employee is different according to their field. So that each field has a different workload problem. Employees of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat tend to have more workloads and responsibilities than one job with a fairly complicated process. so this causes the employees of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat feel the workload and high pressure to do the job.

Table 1. Weighted Workload

Responden	Weighted Workload	Average Weighted Workload	Categorize
Employee 1	1230	82	Very High
Employee 2	1420	94,6	Very High
Employee 3	640	42,6	Slightly High

Employee 4	1090	72,6	High
Employee 5	985	65,6	High

This is reinforced by the authors with data that has been taken using questionnaires to measure the level of an employee's workload. We can see based on the data above from 5 employees of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat 2 of them have a very high workload, 1 is rather high, and 2 others have a high workload. This proves that there is a relatively different workload for each individual employee. Based on an exploratory analysis of business issues using CRT, three root causes were found that caused unwanted effects. First, the root causes of business problems are completely internal. The Diagile method, in particular, the Current Reality Tree (CRT) (COSTA et al., 2011). This method is supported in explaining the internal and external factors that affect research center management and in prioritizing root causes. Current Reality Trees are constructed to establish a causal flow of logical relationships, linking core conflicts to undesired effects (UE) (Reid et al, 2003). Currently, the cause of excess workload is the absence of a clear Organizational Structure which causes employees to often carry out tasks outside their job description. As a result, there are multiple jobs for some employees. In addition, the shortage of employees causes employees to feel their workload is relatively high. Employees also feel they are getting multiple jobs which causes their workload to be high. A workload is a collection of activities that must be completed systematically by an organizational unit or position holder using job analysis techniques, workload analysis techniques, or other management techniques within a specific time frame in order to obtain information about the work efficiency and effectiveness of an organizational unit. (Anita et al 2013).

Figure 1. Current reality Tree

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resource Management

In a company, of course, requires human resources to manage a company or organization. Human resource management is an activity how an organization or company manages employees such as recruiting, providing compensation and benefits, providing job descriptions, training and development, as well as individual relationships and relationships between divisions. Human Resource Management (HRM) is the process of hiring, training, evaluating, and compensating employees, as well as dealing with labor relations, health and safety, and fairness issues. (Dessler., 2018:3). Human resource management is the use of individuals to achieve

organizational goals (HRM). Human resource professionals face a slew of challenges, including a constantly changing workforce, constant government regulations, and technological revolution. Human resource managers design and implement an integrated HRM system. The six functional areas associated with effective HRM are staffing, human resource development, performance management, compensation, safety and health, and employee and labor relations (Wayne Mondy, 2016:25).

Job Description

A job description is a written statement derived from an analysis of the content of a specific job. It differs from a person specification, which describes the attributes required of an employee to do the job to the required standard rather than the job content (Cushway ,2003:2). Taking the time to write a thorough job description will save you both time and money. These are some of the advantages to be gained. (Martin.,2010:12):

- The job description can be used during the recruiting process. If you take the time to define exactly what you want in a candidate, writing a job posting will become easier and clearer.
- It will become an indispensable tool for finding the right candidate. You will not be able to find what you are looking for unless you know exactly what you are looking for in a candidate. Once you've defined the job's definition and requirements, interviewing and judging candidates will become much more focused and, as a result, objective.
- It can be used to bridge the communication gap between the supervisor or manager and the new employee.

Organizational Structure

The organizational structure is the most important part of a company because the organizational structure serves to regulate, control and differentiate the parts within the department. organizational structure is a pattern of work and work groups in an organization that play a role and influence the behavior of individuals and groups (James.,2012:396). According to UEFA (2018) Football's upper management requires a professional team to continuously improve management standards, achieve an organizational level that will improve economic and financial opportunities, bring more discipline and rationality to football accounting, and achieve effective management and organizational skills through football revenue.

Workload

Workload analysis is a process that aims to determine the appropriate number of human resources and responsibilities or workloads for an employee. The workload is a set or number of activities that an organizational unit or position holder must complete within a specific time frame. Because workload is important for a company/institution, the company can find out to what extent its employees can be given the maximum workload and the importance of its influence on the company's performance by providing an effective workload (Tjiabrata et al., 2017). The workload is the amount of work performed by a position/organizational unit and is calculated as the product of work volume and time norm. Boredom will arise if the worker's ability exceeds the job requirements. More fatigue, on the other hand, will appear if the worker's power is lower than the job's demands. Employee workload can be classified into three types: workload that meets standards, workload that is too high (over capacity), and workload that is too low (under power) (Neksen et al, 2021).

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

The data collected in this study is in the form of a questionnaire designed to measure employee workload using the NASA-TLX method as a preliminary. To further deepen this research, the authors used the Semi Structured Interview method with employees, and Root Cause Analysis using the Current Reality Tree (CRT) to find out the root causes of the problems that occur. The data collected is as follows:

- 1 Distribution of questionnaires
The NASA-TLX questionnaire was used in this study to determine the workload experienced by marketing division employees of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat.
- 2 Semi Structured Interview
Interviews were conducted to find out the personal data of each operator and find out the complaints felt by employees of the marketing division of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat.
- 3 Root Cause Analysis using Current Reality Tree (CRT)
An analysis of the causes of excess workload is carried out using the Current Reality Tree (CRT) method to ascertain and describe the causes of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat.

After the process of collecting employee workload data using questionnaires and direct interviews, the next step is data processing using the NASA-TLX method and the results of the Semi Structure Interview, the authors carry out an analysis and proposed solution from the results of employee workload data processing.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysis Job Description

In analyzing the job description data, the author found a finding where in making job descriptions the marketing division PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat did not fulfil the job specification factor. According to (Spencer, 1993) to determine job specifications for a particular position, there are five factors that can be used to further strengthen prospective employees with the job they will be holding so that there was ambiguity regarding the duties and responsibilities to be carried out by employees. for marketing designer positions in this position they often get design jobs outside the marketing division such as getting jobs to design merchandise. The following is a job description below table for the marketing division of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat.

Table 2. Job Description Analysis

Division	Marketing (Partnership and activation)	
Responsibilities	Responsible for handing B2B sales team in achieving revenue and managing client relationship.	
	Responsible for handling partners enquires and facilitate brand activation in professional manners.	
Activities	Business Analyst	Job description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with Business Intelligence Manager to identify, analyze, and provide recommendations regarding on-going business trends. • Perform data gathering and analysis related to PERSIB fans insight, membership dynamics, content performance, and sponsorship activities. • Plan development projects for PERSIB and its commercial partners.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce project report for PERSIB activations, development initiatives, and sponsorship activations. • Support the commercial department in securing and managing brand projects with partners. • checking into the stadium and helping events for activation
	Business Intelligence Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with partnership operations to plan brand activations strategy. • Plan, coordinate and supervise all activities related to the design, development, and implementation of organizational reporting and analytics. • Responsible for maintaining, supporting, and upgrading reports, dashboards, cubes. • data warehouse
	Fans Engagement Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan corporate activations and strategy • Build engagement with communities • Implementing fans education through various activations • work on sponsorship needs
	Activations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Execute corporate and brand activations • Maintaining relationships with players, officials, KOL and other parties • be part of the documentation and edit the video from the activation results.
	Marketing Designer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating visual for corporate, brands, store, and academy. • merchandise design for jersey design • marketing strategy decks

Analysis Organizational Structure

In conducting an analysis of the organizational structure of the author benchmarking with 3 big clubs. Benchmarking is first and foremost an improvement tool, achieved through comparison with other organizations that are recognized as the best in their field. According to the comparison philosophy, a person must be able to recognize his shortcomings and recognize when he does a better job (Faizul, 1999).

Figure 3. Analysis Organizational Structure

Based on analysis Organizational Structure material in this study is the organizational structure, especially for the marketing division (partnership and activation) of merchandise based on the organizational structure benchmarking of club management, the marketing division (partnership and activation) in which there are several positions that should not be lumped together in one division or sub-division. so it is required to create a special division for business analysts, create a special division for managing sponsors, create a special division for activation division and create a special division for merchandise sales.

Business Solutions

Alternative Solution I (New Job Description)

Based on tthe current job description (Table 2) does not have clear job specifications and does not meet 5 factors, namely job information, core competency, managerial competency, functional competency, technical competency, and working condition. So that makes employees feel confused with the actual job description. with the job 5 factors of the job specification it will be easier to measure competency in holding the responsibilities of a given job. The following table below are an example of a new proposed alternative job description for the marketing division:

Table 3. Proposed new Job Description

Job Information
Job Tittle: Business Analyst
Department: Marketing
Direct Reports: Director of Business Development
Job Summary: Business analyst duties are responsible for bridging the gap between information technology (IT) and business by assessing processes, defining requirements, and providing data-driven recommendations and reports to executives and stakeholders or companies according to existing goals and plans, revising presentations, and building shared standards with the Research & Development Unit.

Task and Responsibilities		Performance Indicator	
Identify & analyze business trend		Work with Business Intelligence Manager to identify, analyze, and provide recommendations regarding on-going business trends.	
Analyze dynamics activities data		Perform data gathering and analysis related to PERSIB fans insight, membership dynamics, content performance, and sponsorship activities.	
Plan project partners		Plan development projects for PERSIB and its commercial partners.	
Project Report		Produce project report for PERSIB activations, development initiatives, and sponsorship activations.	
Managing Brand Partners		Support the commercial department in securing and managing brand projects with partners.	
Job Prerequisites Core Competency	Level	Description	
(INT) Initiative	6	Acts up to 1-2 years ahead	
(SCT) Self Control	4	Manages stress effectively	
(ACH) Achievement	6	Makes cost-benefit analyses	
(DEV) Development	4	Give specific positive or mixed feedback for developmental purpose	
Job Prerequisites Managerial Competency	Level	Description	
(IMP) Impact	5	Calculates a dramatic action	
(DIR) Directiveness	5	Obviously monitors performance	
(TL) Team Leadership	2	Informs people	
Job Prerequisites Functional Competency	Level	Description	
(FLX) Flexibility	6	Adapts strategies	
(CSO) Customer Satisfaction Oriented	7	Uses a long-term perspective	
(SCF) Self Confidence	3	States confidence in own ability	
(INFO) Information	5	Does research	
(AT) Analytical Thinking	6	Makes extremely complex plans or analyses	
(IU) Intelligence Understand	5	Acts to help	
(OA) Organizational Awareness	6	Understand long-term underlying issues	
(RB) Relation Building	4	Builds rapport	
(TW) Team work	2	Shares information	
(CO) Competence	5	Monitors data or projects	
(CT) Conceptual Thinking	2	Recognizes patterns	
(OC) Organizational Commitment	3	Sense of purpose-states commitment	
(EXP) Expertise	6	Seasoned professional	
Job Prerequisites Technical Competency	Level	Description	
Experience	2	1-2 years	
Education	4	S1	

Job Prerequisites Working Condition	Level	Description
Comfort Level	4	There will be a high possibility to get pressure while doing the job. Abnormal work rhythm (often work overtime/outside of shift).
Accident Risk Level	1	There won't be an interaction with heavy machinery. Machinery hazard non-existing.
Hazardous Environmental Level	1	The possibility to expose by physical hazardous (chemical/biological/machinery hazard) was very low; almost non-existing. Non-physically demanding job. Working in personal room office (AC) with good humidity level, good air circulation and enough lightning.

Alternative Solution II (New Organizational Structure)

Reengineering completely redesigns an organizations key work processes in order to improve the connection and coordination of various jobs. This workflow integration results in a more responsive and faster execution of tasks. Reengineering is frequently performed through the use of new information technology that enables staff to more effectively regulate and coordinate work processes. The term reengineering refers to the act of fundamentally rethinking and radical redesigning corporate processes in order to generate dramatic performance improvements (Cummings, et.al 2015). Reengineering does not change the overall organizational structure reengineering solves the problem by breaking down specific work units into cross-functional work units to make them more integrated, as well as simplifying work processes and making them more efficient in order to save energy and time. The redesign of this structure is also an effort to improve the work life balance of employees so that they can work optimally without excessive stress. The proposed new organizational structure is based on an analysis of results from internal human resources as well as job descriptions to determine each employees workload.

Figure 4. Proposed Organizational Structure For The Marketing Division Of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat

The proposed organizational structure is the addition of divisions including business intelligence, business analysis, partnership and activation divisions, as well as merchandise and retail divisions which are under the leadership of the director of business development. where in the previous organizational structure the position was part of the Partnership division and activation in this case would make the employee feel confused about the position and position held so that it was possible to get multiple jobs outside

of the specified position. For the division proposed by the author, the previous division still handles the partnership and activation division as well as the Persib Store.

Alternative Solution III (Recruitment Potential Candidate)

Based on the results of the organizational structure analysis and job descriptions and the root cause analysis of marketing division employees. Marketing employees have a high workload due to the lack of employees in the division. Therefore, this report aims to provide sensitivity to the leadership of the importance of increasing the capacity of the marketing division of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat. This additional workforce can be offered to reduce the workload felt and faced by employees of the marketing division of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat and tailored to the needs of the company. Based on the proposed new organizational alternative (Figure 3) by creating new divisions, a minimum of 6 new candidates are needed to fill the new divisions that have been created.

Alternative Solution IV (Internship Program)

Judging from the root of the problems faced by the marketing division of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat is an excessive workload due to a shortage of employees which causes the employee's workload to increase. Interns can fill in and assist in the business analyst, partnership & sponsorship, and activation sub-divisions. Apprenticeship program availability can be divided into several categories:

1. Managing trend from data in business analyst

The internship program can be opened every time there is an opening of an internship program from campuses in Bandung. Intern students can help, starting from helping to identify & analyze business trends, project reports, and managing brand partners. The intern student's final task is to make a report on what needs to be repaired from the project plan that will be used, which can then be used as a performance report database from PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat.

2. Analysis of agreement between partnership and PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat

Acceptance of apprentice students can be adjusted according to the activation event schedule that will be carried out by PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat which is adjusted to the needs of the division. These apprentice students will later be able to help the partnership and sponsorship division to prepare for maintaining relationships with sponsors and make planning projects to get sponsors.

3. Activate for brand or product promotion

Acceptance of apprentice students can be adjusted according to the activation event schedule that will be carried out by PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat which is tailored to the needs of the team. These intern students can later help the activation division to prepare

Alternative Solution IV (Internship Program)

In carrying out the recruitment process, of course, costs are needed to be able to recruit the employees needed and adjusted to company criteria. To be able to minimize the costs to be incurred by the company the author provides a solution to prioritize which divisions should be prioritized in recruiting by looking at the company's fundamentals such as the vision and mission of the company, adjusting to the job descriptions of each division and the number of employees from each division. The author uses the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) method to determine the priority of the recruitment process which is more valid. According to (Suwarsono et al. 2016) Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a method used to analyze and determine complex decisions. This method can explain how priorities are at a higher level and can affect priorities at a lower level. The following (figure 4) below is the result of the calculation of the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) for the process of recruiting employees for the marketing division of PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat.

Figure 5. AHP Calculation

Based on (Figure 4) above, it can be concluded that to carry out the employee recruitment process, the business analyst division is the company's main priority, adjusted to the conditions that exist within the company. By using this method the costs for recruiting employees are not too high because the recruitment process is carried out by looking at what the company is prioritizing.

CONCLUSION

Unstructured and unclear organizational structure and job descriptions as well as the presence of job-related information from each position can affect the effectiveness of the productivity and workload of marketing employees at PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat, as evidenced by the results of distributing questionnaires to employees using the NASA-TLX method and direct interviews with employees. The conclusions in this chapter will answer the research questions listed in the first chapter.

1. Based on the organizational assessment, the main problem faced by PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat is the unclear organizational structure and lack of job-related information for their positions. resulting in employees often getting jobs outside of the predetermined job descriptions, because employees get jobs outside of job descriptions, and the reality of the current conditions where employees feel the workload they face is quite high.
2. In order to overcome the problems that PT. Persib Bandung Bermartabat is currently facing and prepare them to support their strategic initiatives to reduce the workload they face, the strategy that the author intends is to formulate a new organizational structure, job description for the company, hiring potential candidate, internship program, and prioritizing.

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